

UDK 372.881

**CULTURAL-BASED APPROACH IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AND FOREIGN
LANGUAGES AT UNIVERSITY THROUGH LITERARY TEXTS**

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Abstract. *The article studies the cultural-based approach in teaching Russian and foreign languages at University through the deliberate work with national-and-cultural vocabulary layer, texts excerpts which reveal specific details of everyday life, history and culture of different people. Texts reflect the spiritual world of a person and indicate a direct connection with culture, store information about history, ethnography, national psychology and national behavior, that is, about everything that makes up the content of culture. Such approach means the connection of language and culture in the process of formation of communicative and cultural-study competences by students, enrichment of learners' vocabulary with cultural peculiarities and components, art-study terms, development of coherent speech, making prerequisites for communication in social and cultural environment. Cultural-based approach can be used as a teaching tool, as it includes the necessary content: folklore, customs and traditions, art, painting, architecture, music, cinema, theatre, fiction, mass media; familiarization with geography, history.*

Key words: *cultural-based competence, cultural-based text, approach, method, tolerance, communicative competence.*

Introduction

The process of teaching Russian and English languages on the cognitive basis, i.e. minimalized reality, in which interconnection between culture of different nations is considered, allows stand out culture-study competence as the main part of communicative competence. It is meant the understanding of language as the form of national culture expression, interconnection between language and history of a nation, specific features of Russian and English, mastery of speech etiquette standards.

Methodology actively works at cultural-based approach in teaching languages on the wide cultural and country study background. By cultural-based approach L.A. Khodyakova understands the acquisition of the life experience of the nature, their culture (national traditions, religion, moral and aesthetic values, art) and the spiritual and aesthetic impact on the thoughts, feelings, behavior, and actions of students in the process of studying the language [1, 2018, p. 94]. According to S.G. Ter-Minasova, "language is a mirror of culture, it reflects not only the real world surrounding a person, not only the real conditions of his life, but also the social self-awareness of the people, their mentality, national character, way of life, traditions, customs, morality, value system, worldview, vision of the world" [2, 2006, p. 21]. Mentality, national picture of the world and specific character traits are most clearly manifested in language. M. Byram's theory is distinguished by a positive attitude to the use of information about native culture in foreign language classes. "Co-study of native and foreign cultures" is the main advantage of this theory. "Thanks to such contrastive and comparative study, students better understand their own culture, its features, begin to recognize themselves as cultural and historical subjects and master the culture of the country of the foreign language." [3, 1997, p. 48]. D. Shanahan marks the role of learning material of culture and literature

that should “include the specific ways in which language and literature may encode culture and have an effective impact of learners in the classroom”. [4, 2011, p. 14]. The role of cultural-based approach approves by M. Gardner who notes that if a teacher uses this approach to the classroom, the learning process can be “a powerful factor in improving student learning, retention, and application. It can also improve the transfer of the education outside of the formal learning environment and into the student’s lives and interests” [5, 2022, p. 2].

The inclusion of a cultural-based component in the university course of Russian and a foreign language allows us to examine the features of the use of linguistic means in a literary text. The linguist classifies texts that reflect the spiritual world of a person as “true keepers of culture” and points out the direct connection between the text and culture, since it is permeated with many cultural codes; it is the text that stores information about history, ethnography, national psychology and national behavior, that is, about everything that constitutes the content of culture. According to V.A. Maslova, “the text is the true junction of linguistics and cultural studies, since it belongs to language and is its highest tier, while at the same time the text is a form of existence of culture” [6, 2004, p. 52]. According to L.A. Khodyakova “studying the text not only from the point of view of language, but also culture, develops in students the ability to independently master cultural values through words, compose their own text in the unity of content and form in accordance with the author’s intention, and practically use the language in various conditions and situations of its application” [1, 2018, p. 92]. We completely agree with M. V. Cherkhezova, who asserts that familiarization with another culture should be based on a solid foundation of the native culture. Only relying on this foundation can we take the next step – to make either comprehend or emotionally experience the phenomena and facts of another culture. When encountering another culture, unlike the native one, what is required first of all is a thorough cultural commentary on the facts and realities of the other culture [7, 2007, p. 53].

This approach in teaching methods means, on the one hand, that learners while studying languages will assimilate life experience of the nations, their culture and traditions and, on the other hand, the formation of moral, ethical and spiritual influence on the thoughts, feelings, behavior, and actions of students themselves. The implementation of the cultural-based approach presupposes the use of basic components of a cultural focus, which recently have been increasingly encountered in the methods of teaching Russian and foreign languages. These are, for example, such terms and concepts as the cultural background of a lesson, a cultural text, an art text, and other kinds of texts.

The relevance of this work is due to the need to develop a person's personality as a keeper, a bearer and a creator of culture. In the context of higher education system, the solution to this problem must be linked primarily with the historical and cultural content in the educational context. Thus, cultural-based competence in teaching Russian and foreign languages becomes one of the most significant means of spiritual and moral development of students, the formation of their national self-awareness and the system of universal human values.

Based on the mentioned above, *the object* of our study is the formation of cultural-based competence. As a *subject* of the study, we consider the methods of forming students' cultural-based competence in Russian and foreign language lessons using literary texts. *The purpose of the study* is to develop a methodological system for forming this competence at the lessons of the Russian and English languages.

In our opinion, the cultural-based approach allows to combine language learning with understanding the culture of a nation and taking into account the regional component, which is designed to ensure that students comprehend facts specific to a particular region. In the context of the higher education system, the solution to this problem must be closely connected to the historical and cultural content of the educational context. The experience of long-term coexistence of the Russian and Kazakh peoples creates conditions for the interpenetration of cultures and familiarization with the peculiarities of another culture based on the idea of tolerance. Cultural-based competence in teaching Russian and foreign languages in universities of Kazakhstan is speech etiquette; stable combinations and expressions; customs and traditions; historical events and landmarks; famous

works of art and literature; well-known personalities; manifestation of the mentality of different peoples (behavior, actions, deeds, character types).

Excerpts from the works by Kazakhstani writers and poets (Abai, Sh. Ualikhanov, Vs. Ivanov, P. Vasiliev, S. Seifullin, M. Auezov, M. Zverev, B. Kanap'yanov, O. Suleimenov, Yu. Dombrovsky, etc.) can be used as didactic material in the lessons of Russian and foreign languages. Such texts by Kazakhstani authors will not only help students to better understand the history, culture, and traditions of peoples, but will also provide an opportunity to study the specific features of the language, be tolerant to other people and later use vocabulary that reflects the realities of Kazakhstan in various communication situations.

Thus, the result of the cultural-based approach can be the formation of the cultural-based competence of students, i.e. understanding the language, national history and culture of their people, the awareness of the originality and uniqueness of their traditions and customs.

Material and methods

In the frame of our research we have used the following methods: descriptive-analytical (analysis of pedagogical, psychological, and linguistic concepts); study the scientific and teaching-and-methodological literature on the research topic; socio-pedagogical (monitor real learning activity of students at lessons); methods of linguistic analyses of textual material, experimental.

Monitoring a regional component in teaching Russian and foreign languages is important at each working stage but the most meaningful is the selection of regional material. In our opinion, literary texts of regional (Kazakhstani) writers are the culture keeping, and the analysis of the texts must be widened from the monitoring the language units' function in texts up to the broad context mentioning "out-of-text sphere".

Cultural-based material in Russian and foreign language lessons will be literary texts that tell about historical events, national culture, customs and traditions of different peoples, nature, character and morals, the problem of "purity" and speech culture. The use of such texts that reveal the peculiarities of the worldview of different nations contributes to the development of patriotism and tolerance, respect for people of all nationalities.

The certainty of the communicational topics will allow to foresee nationally specific objects and phenomena, features of the national mentality and national behavior, revealed on the basis of comparison of the realities of Kazakhstan. Any speech topics are suitable for creating speech situations in which the place of the event can be a city, village, a certain region of Russia, Kazakhstan and Great Britain, the interlocutor (interlocutors) are unofficial or official persons of different ages from different countries.

Attention to the cultural-based competence does not mean that less time will be left for the formation of other types of competences, does not lead to overloading of students, to complication of the program. On the contrary, the creation of a cultural environment in teaching Russian and foreign languages ensures the unity of the process of all types of competences formation, all types of speech activity, and the unity of training and education.

All of the above does not claim to be an exhaustive definition of what constitutes the cultural-based competence. Undoubtedly, its formation is associated with a good knowledge of precedent texts, music, and painting. Consequently, developing such competence means developing memory, being able to work with dictionaries, reference books, and works of fiction, and feeling the need to refer to them in order to constantly replenish one's spiritual and cultural baggage.

Results. Discussion

The use of cultural-based information ensures an increase in the cognitive activity of students, expands their communicative capabilities, promotes the creation of positive motivation, and helps solve educational problems. Literary texts with their emotional coloring, make students as witnesses of the described events related to the history or traditions of the country, introduce them to the specific side of the language and culture of Kazakhstan and abroad, being the most significant means of assimilating the information received.

The purpose and objectives of the work allowed us to define the stages of the study: at the first stage, materials for diagnostic sections were developed, including questionnaires for students, diagnostic tasks checking the level of formation by students' cultural competence. The diagnostic stage of the experiment was conducted.

The second stage is the results of the ascertaining sections were analyzed. Based on the data obtained, an approach to the formation of cultural-based competence was substantiated, allowing for the interconnected formation of knowledge about national and cultural specifics in relation to the levels of linguistic personality and linguistic mentality. A methodological system of work on the formation of cultural competence of students was developed.

At the third stage, we have tested the developed methodological system for the formation of cultural-based competence in experimental training.

Students from two groups studying Russian and English participated in the survey. The results of the study showed that all students (100%) recognize the need and possibility of forming cultural-based competence in Russian and foreign language lessons. At the same time, 75% of respondents have difficulties in their work caused by the lack of specialized literature on this issue, since the methodological materials do not provide a full range of tasks using texts on the material of a foreign language. 25% of the students surveyed record insufficient training in the field of working with cultural texts as a difficulty, since during the work, attention is paid to teaching the subject rather than finding forms of presenting cultural information. 80% of students agreed that careful selection of the content of the educational material will contribute to the development of cultural-based competence.

The carried out work has showed that the problem of implementing the cultural-based approach with the help of literary text excerpts in the process of teaching Russian and a foreign language requires experimental testing of effective ways of using text for the purpose of developing cultural-based competence. The work in Russian and foreign language lessons was carried out on the material of micro texts from the works of Vsevolod Ivanov and the poetry of Abai Kunanbayev, respectively. The choice of texts by these writers is not accidental. Vsevolod Ivanov is our fellow countryman, born in the village of Lebyazhye, Pavlodar district, Semipalatinsk province, studied at the Pavlodar lower agricultural school, worked in the Pavlodar printing house - first as a spinner of a hand-held printing machine, and then mastered the typesetting craft. Not only the passion for the specific features of Kazakhstani nature inspired the artist of words to create works. He was attracted by the freedom-loving spirit of the Kazakh people, their impulse to fight for a better life. Trying to master the Kazakh theme in literature, the writer showed a desire to carefully study and use materials from the life, history, and culture of the Kazakh people.

Abai Kunanbaev is widely considered the greatest writer of Kazakhstan. His impact on literature and culture is rather immeasurable. His prolific output includes lots of poems, novels, and witty idioms that have become the legacy of Kazakhstani people and abroad. To the 175-th anniversary of the poet at the foreign languages department the contest of poems' best translation into English was arranged.

We have done some work to develop cultural-based competence. For a month, students in Russian and foreign language classes worked with texts related to one of the outstanding literary figures. The work began with a comprehensive analysis of the biographical text. In the following classes, work was carried out with micro texts, sentences, individual cards, reports, messages related to the life and work by Vs. Ivanov and Abai. The texts of the works, nurturing an aesthetic sense, patriotism and tolerance, created a special atmosphere and cultural background in the classes.

Local language material is harmoniously included in the content of the educational process. A special place in the formation of cultural-based competence is occupied by familiarization with ethnographic realities (realities of everyday life, customs, traditions, plants, animals, the environment, etc.). Deciphering the ancient names of cities and villages mentioned in a literary text, clarifying ethnographic, everyday realities - all these and many other aspects of the creative search of students are based on interdisciplinary connections. Assignments for exercises can be as follows: "Read the text, what historical realities are found in it? Using a dictionary, explain their meanings"; "Name the

archaisms found in the fiction text. What details of everyday life do they denote?"; "Prepare a message about the traditions and customs of the Russian and Kazakh peoples based on the material of the fiction text." "What terms denoting elements of everyday life and realities of the Kazakh people require additional interpretation when translating them into English?", "Find synonyms for the underlined words?", etc.

Among the productive types of tasks that promote the activation of students' speech activity, we can name *situational role-playing games*. The form of conducting a lesson based on the use of a role-playing game depends largely on the specific topic. We have conducted lessons in the form of an excursion, a meeting, a trip, a TV show ("Around the cities of Kazakhstan", "Kazakhstan's land", "Interview with a famous writer"). During the game "Kazakhstan's land", students build a route map for a correspondence trip through the settlements of Kazakhstan. The works by Vs. Ivanov contain names of cities, towns, villages, rivers, lakes, mountains, e.g. cities like Pavlodar, Ekibastuz, Petropavlovsk, Ust-Kamenogorsk, Kokchetav, Semipalatinsk, Turkestan, Verny, Orenburg, the villages of Lebyazhye and Yamyshevo, Volchikha, the Irtysh River, Lake Alakol, the Kara-Su mountain stream, the Isyk-Tau gorge, the Tarbagatai mountains, etc. The texts about Abai Kunanbayev clearly show the path of social development of the Kazakh steppe, the problems of nomads. The language material using by students in the role-playing game should be introduced at earlier stages of training.

When teaching Russian and foreign languages, we use the method of *comparative analysis*, which is based on the comparative-historical study of language. Analyzing a text, students consider a word not only in synchronous reality, but also in diachronic reality, referring to the etymology of the word, to the changes that have occurred with words during their "life" in the language system.

We can refer to a text containing information about the historical realities of the past, and then compose your own text telling about similar phenomena and realities of today. Let's compare the description of the village of Lebyazhye in 1930 and today: "In Lebyazhye, instead of a policeman, there is a village chieftain, instead of a progymnasium, a city school and an agricultural school, there is Vyacheslav Ivanov with his three dozen students. But near the high sandy bank in Lebyazhye there is the same pier as in Pavlodar, and behind the village there are several mills, burial mounds, and a steppe. There is not a single tree along the street, and always, whenever and however long I have been there, a calf walks along the street..." [8, 1985, p. 323].

When working on fiction texts, we use the technique of culturally oriented word analysis. The teacher's task is to orient students to the specific realities of people's lives; to show how the features of national culture and the worldview of the people are reflected in the word, i.e. to extract all the cultural information that the given word has accumulated. In English literature lessons, when studying the legend of King Arthur and his round table, students could see a clear connection between different cultures, i.e. at the example of the Round Table existing in ancient England in the 8th century and the same object of everyday life used by Kazakh people by centuries with the same meaning of unity, equality, and tolerance.

In the text by Vs. Ivanov, students were able to trace the peculiarities of celebrating Maslenitsa in the city of Pavlodar at the beginning of the 20th century by representatives of the Russian and Kazakh peoples: "The city was preparing for Maslenitsa. The Maslenitsa festivities go around two streets that look like a pretzel, past the base, the cathedral, the progymnasium, the merchants' yards and two hotels. The streets are filled with sleds, sledges and sledges. Some are decorated with carpets, and the poorer owners with embroidered felt mats. The carriages go in a tight crowd. The wooden sidewalks are filled with townswomen, Cossacks and Kyrgyz. People have pulled out all their best clothes. Here they boast of their horses, fur coats, the number of children, and some families have set out on several sleds at once" [9, 1985, p. 175].

Abai's "The words of wisdom" is the fundamental literary work consisting of 45 brief parables and philosophical treatises. This prose poem raises issues of national education and worldview, morality and law, and the history of the Kazakhs. Each parable has a particular meaning and can be used at the lessons differently, e.g. in "Word Four" the author analyses the meaning of *foolish*

laughter which “resembles drunkenness”, and anyone who “constantly indulged in *senseless merriment* ignores his conscience, neglects his affairs and commits unforgiveable blunders. Even a “kind laughter that does not come from heart burst out in hollow pearls just for the sake of forced jollity. Only labour makes a person happy. [10, 2012, p. 2]. This parable teaches learners not only to be honest and hard-working but also pay attention to some lexical and stylistic features of English grammar and syntax like word-formation, cleft-sentences, metaphors, etc.

Having performed various types of exercises based on literary texts, students demonstrated the ability to systematically represent the culture of different nations; to draw associative links between objects and phenomena in different cultural traditions; to comment on the ethno-cultural use of linguistic units of different levels in a literary text. Also while studying Russian and a foreign language based on ethno-culturally rich literary texts, students became familiar with the national-linguistic picture of the world of different nations.

In order to master the culture of speech behavior, it is significant to understand the essence of speech etiquette as an indicator of a person's upbringing, his background, and business traits of character. A rich set of linguistic means makes it possible to choose a form of communication which can be appropriate for a speech situation and favorable for the addressee in a lesson, to establish a friendly, relaxed or, on the contrary, official tone of conversation. It is important to emphasize that speech etiquette conveys social information about the speaker and his addressee, whether they know each other or not, about the relationship of equality/inequality in age, official position, about their personal relationships (if they know each other), about the setting (official/informal) in which communication takes place, etc.

The conducted research showed an increased interest for Russian and foreign language lessons (74% of students note Russian and foreign language lessons among the most interesting). The cognitive activity of students in class and out-of-class time has soared (46% of students have a high level of cognitive activity; 48% - average; 6% - low). Positive growth is also observed in the development of verbal and logical thinking of students. (15% of students have a high level of development of verbal and logical thinking, above average - 55%; average - 24%; below average - 6%; there are no students with a low level).

Thus, the experimental training has shown that the inclusion of cultural studies material in the content of teaching Russian and a foreign language contributes to the formation of the following minimum knowledge and skills in students: a) ideas about language as a cultural and historical environment that embodies the history, culture, customs, and traditions of a region; b) skills to analyze the surrounding language environment, evaluate the speech of interlocutors, and contribute to the improvement of their speech culture; c) skills to understand the structural and semantic features of Russian and a foreign language; d) knowledge of proper names, including toponyms and microtoponyms; skills to explain their origin in oral and written speech; d) skills to use figurative and expressive means of language in speech; e) skills to coherently express one's thoughts on regional topics (nature, economics, culture (including linguistic), adequate to a natural communication situation; g) knowledge of speech etiquette issues (of a certain city, region).

In our opinion, the cultural approach presupposes the implementation of a connection with literature, since in Russian and foreign language lessons it is necessary to consider the peculiarities of the use of words in the works of writers. This creates in the lesson that aesthetic environment that is perceived by students as a natural environment, since words will subsequently be used in the conditions of natural communication.

Conclusion

Thus, the cultural approach to teaching Russian and foreign languages involves studying language as a result, a product of human cultural development. Language is considered as an integral part of culture, forming national self-awareness. The result of the cultural approach can be the formation of students' cultural competence. Cultural competence becomes one of the most important means of developing the spiritual and moral world of students, forming their national self-awareness and establishing a system of universal human values.

Doing research, we came to the conclusion that Russian and foreign language lessons using texts on Kazakh topics should be aimed at students' mastering the basic norms and rules of speech design, obtaining certain information about the history, culture, and traditions of their native land, using lexical and grammatical material in speech that characterizes the geographical, natural, and climatic features of the region, etc. Using local language material implies the possibility of integrated lessons, excursion lessons, role-playing games, creative competitions, and travel lessons. Based on local material, a series of creative tasks are developed to analyze and reconstruct the text in speech development lessons. The educational text should be the highest unit of teaching speech activity and contribute to the solution of communicative problems in specific forms and situations of communication using linguistic means.

A literary text is a treasure trove of knowledge about the culture and history of a nation, a reflection of this culture and history, and at the same time the result of a person's spiritual activity. During linguistic work, students not only observe how a word "lives" and "works" in a literary text, but also learn the art of attentive, thoughtful reading, which becomes "co-creation with the author."

The culture-based approach presents culture in all its complicity and diversity, creates conditions for enriching students with information about culture; helps to form their own cultural self-awareness, attitudes towards other cultures; calls on each person to care about preserving cultural diversity, avoiding forceful interventions in nature and social relations. To be good at Russian and foreign languages, to have the ability to communicate on various topics, and to achieve success in the communication process are those personal characteristics that largely determine a person's achievements in almost all areas of life and contribute to his social adaptation to the changing conditions of the modern world.

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